

PERBEDAAN MODEL PEMBELAJARAN KOOPERATIF TIPE *TEAMS GAMES TOURNAMENT* DAN *MAKE A MATCH* TERHADAP HASIL BELAJAR

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk mengetahui: (1) Rata-rata hasil belajar siswa menggunakan tipe *Teams Games Tournament*; (2) Rata-rata hasil belajar siswa menggunakan tipe *Make a Match*; dan (3) Perbedaan rata-rata hasil belajar siswa antara tipe *Teams Games Tournament* dan *Make a Match*. Metode penelitian eksperimen dengan bentuk penelitian *quasi experimental design*. Rancangan *non equivalent control group design*. Sampel berjumlah 55 siswa. Instrumen penelitian berupa tes pilihan ganda. Analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif dan inferensial. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan: (1) Rata-rata hasil belajar siswa menggunakan tipe *Teams Games Tournament* adalah 79,89; (2) Rata-rata hasil belajar siswa menggunakan tipe *Make A Match* adalah 84,52; dan (3) Perbedaan rata-rata hasil belajar siswa antara tipe *Teams Games Tournament* dan *Make A Match* menunjukkan nilai sig. sebesar 0,048. Dengan taraf kepercayaan 5% disimpulkan bahwa terdapat perbedaan antara model pembelajaran kooperatif tipe *Teams Games Tournament* dan *Make A Match* terhadap hasil belajar siswa.

Kata Kunci: Pembelajaran Kooperatif, Tipe *Teams Games Tournament*, Tipe *Make A Match*, Hasil Belajar.

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out: (1) The mean score of the students learning outcomes by using Teams Games Tournament; (2) The mean score of the students learning outcomes by using Make a Match; and (3) The difference mean score between Teams Games Tournament and Make a Match. The method used in this research was quasi experimental design. This research was non- equivalent control group design. The sample was 55 students. The research instrument was a multiple choice test. The data were analyzed by using descriptive and inferential analysis. The results showed that: (1) The mean score of the students learning outcomes by using Teams Games Tournament was 79.89; (2) The mean score of the students learning outcomes by using Make a Match was 84.52; and (3) Difference mean score between Teams Games Tournament and Make a Match was 0,048 at level significance of 5%. It was concluded that there was a difference between the cooperative learning models of the Teams Games Tournament and Make a Match on student learning outcomes.

Keywords: Cooperative Learning, Type of *Teams Games Tournament*, Type of *Make A Match*, Learning Outcomes.